

PRAGMATIC FAILURE IN INTERPRETING SOME ENGLISH PROVERBS INTO UZBEK LANGUAGE

Kudratova Sitora Rashidovna

BSMI, the teacher of English language department

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10041408>

Abstract. *This article deals with Pragma-linguistic issues while translating some types of phraseological units from English into Uzbek which are sayings, proverbs, phrases, stable and free combinations. All of those are different in each country which depends on the history of creation and the ways that individuals express in their lifestyle. There are given different equivalents of phraseological units into Uzbek language.*

Keywords: *phraseological units, Pragma-linguistic issues, proverbs, phrases, translate, English phrase, Uzbek language.*

Introduction. Pragma-linguistic is one of the developing directions in today's linguistics. Pragmatics means "action" by translating from Greek. Hence, its subject is the language in use. In philosophy and psychology, this term is used to refer to action, practice. Linguistic pragmatics is a language that is studied as a means of "use within itself, not for itself". While interpreting some text or even simultaneous interpreting occurs some pragmatic problems in speech. Such pragma-linguistic problems related to the addressees with their specific socio-cultural knowledge and horizon.

Methodology. Several research methods used in this research, such as comparison, description, classification, textual analysis.

Proverbs have another feature, which is that the speech act can also be the main factor causing the occurrence, that is, the main load forming the content of the speech act can be assigned to the proverb. Let's take English phrase "hot under the collar", if we translate it literally into Uzbek it looks like as "yoqa ostidagi issiqlik", however, the equivalent of it in Uzbek language is "tepa sochi tikka bo'lmoq", since that phraseological unit means "angry or embarrassed". Thus, there are several types of phraseological units that can be converted into other languages:

Using phraseological Equivalent

Because of the influence of religion, culture and way of life of people, it is sometimes difficult to translate phraseological units from one language into another. In this case, translators need to find analogue or equivalent proverb in target language. For instance:

Don't put all your eggs in one basket – this proverb means that everybody should carefully take something into consideration before making a decision, otherwise its results may harm. So, if we translate it word-to-word into Uzbek this looks as following – "hamma tuxumlarni bitta savatga qo'yma". From literal translation it is difficult to catch up its core meaning. So that, to find the equivalent proverb in Uzbek language is the only way to deliver its meaning to listeners. "Suvni ko'rmay, etikni yechma" or "boringni biringga tikma" can be equivalents of that proverb. "Birds of a feather flock together" – *O'xshatmasdan uchratmas* (They do not meet who do not look like each other

"A friend in court is better than a penny in purse" – *Boylik boylik emas, birlik boylik* (Wealth is not wealth, solidarity is wealth).

Absolute Equivalent

There are the some proverbs in English which can be translated into absolute style into Uzbek language.

"A watched pot never boils" - *kutilgan qozon qaynamas*

"Wisdom is the beauty of men" - *odam bezagi aql* (beauty of man is his wisdom)

"Manners make the man" - *insonni fazilatlar ulug'laydi* (Manners earns reputation for man)

The Uzbek translation of above phraseological units is absolutely the same with their original one. Not only connotative meaning, but also their grammatical structures are similar with those texts in source language.

Similar Equivalent

"All bread is not baked in one oven" - *hamma non ham bitta tandirda yopilgan emas*. In this proverb, the word "oven" translated as "tandir". Due to the fact that the word "tandir" is foreign to English people, it is translated as "oven" which is the similar analogue of that word.

Use direct translation

"All are not saint that go to the church" - *cherkovga borganlarning hammasi ham avliyo bo'lavermaydi*. Here all words translated with their independent meaning which called as direct translation. Literally to say, even though this proverb is very specific to Christian nations because of the word "church", we can easily translate it in the way of word-to-word, since we have the same concept of that word "cherkov".

"Hope for the best and prepare for the worst" – *yaxshiga umid bog'la, yomonga o'zingni shayla*. As it is clear that, this proverb talks about positive and negative results of a particular action. Due to no equivalent in any source, it was translated through word-to-word style.

Moreover, it is proven that there are several Uzbek equivalents of one English proverb or vice-versa. That can be seen in the following graphs:

Figure 4. Several Uzbek equivalents of one English proverb

All Uzbek proverbs given to the English one are phraseological equivalents. In the proverb “before you choose a friend eat a bushel of salt with him”, the expression “eat a bushel of salt” is taken as the main core of that proverb. So, in the Uzbek proverbs “*sinalmagan*”, “*tandagi po'stm*”, “*safarda bilinar*”, “*kulfatda bilinear*”, “*jonga kuymas*” are brought as equivalent of that expression. However, these proverbs are applied in different contexts according to social and pragmatic factors such as time, place, situation, case, and so on. Here are the literal translations of those Uzbek proverbs:

Do not tell your secrets to your friend that has not been tested.

Do not consider everyone a friend as your skin on your body.

A friend is tested in a trip, brothers in trouble.

A friend is tested in trouble.

A close friend worries about your life, what a friend if he does not worry

The below given graph reveals several English equivalents of an Uzbek proverb

Figure 5. Several English equivalents of an Uzbek proverb

The main point of Uzbek proverb is about “old friend” and its direct translation looks like as following – “*old friendship does not rust*”. All English proverbs in this graph contain the words “*old friend*”. In fact, the expression “*qadim do'stlik*” is converted from Uzbek into English in a way of direct translation. Moreover, due to some additional expressions added in English proverbs (such as *wine, tune, silver gold*) which represent various structural, stylistic and pragmatic features, the usage in different contexts can provide additional expressive or emotional meanings of proverbs.

So, we can say that not all types of phraseological units can easily be translated in some case it is almost impossible, since they are linked to the culture and social system of those nations.

In order to reach a clear and precise translation, interpreters are demanded to possess a rich historical experience of the people, ideas which related with work, lifestyle and culture of people.

REFERENCES

1. Hasanovna, D. M. (2021). Semantic Implementation of resultative structures. novateur publications JournalNX- A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal.
2. Hasanovna, D. M. (2021). Semantic Implementation of resultative structures. novateur publications JournalNX- A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal.
3. Rakhmatova, M. (2022). Академическая честность и плагиат: проблемы воспитания. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 15(15). извлечено от http://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/6966
4. Musinovna M. R., Jakhonovna M. C. SOCIO-CULTURAL PRAGMATICS AS A METHOD OF PEDAGOGICALLY INTERPRETING INTERCULTURAL EXPERIENCES. Conferencea, 148–150. – 2022.
5. Rakhmatova Mekhriniso Muhsinovna, & Usmonov Amon Aminovich. (2022). THE IMPLEMENTATION OF CORPUS-BASED TECHNIQUES TO ANALYZE LITERARY WORKS. Open Access Repository, 8(04), 88–91. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/XDC6U>
6. Musinovna R. M. Academic Integrity: Teaching and Learning Challenges. Integration of Pragmalinguistics, Functional Translation Studies and Language Teaching Processes, 30–33. – 2022.
7. Muhayyo Davlatova. Semantic properties of effective constructions in English and Uzbek languages. E3S Web Conf. Volume 420, 2023 EBWFF 2023 - International Scientific Conference Ecological and Biological Well-Being of Flora and Fauna (Part 1).
8. Davlatova, M. H. RELATION OF LEXICAL-SEMANTIC STRUCTURE OF VERBS TO RESULTABILITY.
9. Rashidovna, K. S. . (2022). The Role of Translation and its Future Perspectives. American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research, 3(9), 186–191. Retrieved from <https://www.globalresearchnetwork.us/index.php/ajshr/article/view/1508>
10. Kudratova Sitora Rashidovna. (2022). THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TRANSLATION AND CULTURE. International Journal Of Literature And Languages, 2(11), 35–42. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ijll/Volume02Issue11-06>
11. Rashidovna, K. S. . (2023). The Influence of Culture on Translation Activities. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF LANGUAGE LEARNING AND APPLIED LINGUISTICS, 2(2), 80–83. Retrieved from <http://inter-publishing.com/index.php/IJLLAL/article/view/1162>
12. Kudratova Sitora Rashidovna. (2023). LINGUISTIC ISSUES IN TRANSLATION. International Journal Of Literature And Languages, 3(02), 29–35. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ijll/Volume03Issue02-07>
13. Anvarovna, Z. D. (2023). APPROACHES TO THE STUDY OF SPEECH VERBS IN MODERN ENGLISH. Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities, 11(5), 457-466.
14. Anvarovna, Z. D. . (2023). Syntagmatic Properties of English Speech Verbs Speak, Talk, Say, Tell. Academic Integrity and Lifelong Learning (France), 152–158. Retrieved from <https://openconference.us/index.php/academic/article/view/705>

15. Ziyoyeva , D. A. (2023). SEMANTICS OF THE SPEECH VERBS SPEAK, TALK IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE. *Innovative Development in Educational Activities*, 2(6), 217–225. Retrieved from <https://openidea.uz/index.php/idea/article/view/912>
16. Anvarovna, Z. D. (2023). The Classification of Speech Verbs in English. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 33, 268-274.
17. Nasriyeva Guzal Zulfiddin Qizi. (2023). DEPICTION OF SOCIAL LIFE IN THE NOVEL “MEHRODDAN CHAYON” BY ABDULLA KADIRI. *International Journal Of Literature And Languages*, 3(04), 88–94. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ijll/Volume03Issue04-16>
18. Nasriyeva Guzal Zulfiddin Qizi. (2023). THE CONCEPT OF TOLERANCE IN ENGLISH MEDIA AND PRESS. *International Journal Of Literature And Languages*, 3(02), 74–81. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ijll/Volume03Issue02-14>
19. Qizi, N. G. Z. (2022). Psychoanalytical Approach in English Literature. *Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture*, 3(12), 34-38. Retrieved from <https://www.cajlpc.centralasianstudies.org/index.php/CAJLPC/article/view/632>
20. Qizi, N. G. Z. . (2022). Literature as Discourse. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 3(10), 266–271. Retrieved from
21. Mirzaeva, A. S. (2022). INTRA-LINGUISTIC AND EXTRA-LINGUISTIC FACTORS RELATED TO THE LANGUAGE AND VOCABULARY OF THE BASIC CONCEPTS OF RENAISSANCE ENGLISH PHILOSOPHY. *Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture*, 1(5), 9-17.
22. Aziza, M. (2022). THE THEORY OF INTERTEXTUALITY AS A PARADIGM AND THE IMPACT OF THIS THEORY ON TRANSLATION. *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research*, 2(5), 990-995.
23. Мирзаева, А. Ш. (2021). РЕМИНИСЦЕНЦИЯ КАК ЭЛЕМЕНТ ИНТЕРТЕКСТУАЛЬНОСТИ В ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИИ РИКА РИОРДАНА “PERCU JACKSON AND THE LIGHTN ING THIEF”. *МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА*, 4(3).
24. Mirzaeva, A. S. (2022). THEORY IN INTERTEXTUALITY AND THREE SEAMLESS INTERTEXTS: M. BUTTERFLV BY DAVID H. HWANG, AS IS BY WILLIAM M. HOFFMAN, AND EXECUTION OF JUSTICE BY EMILY MANN. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(5-2), 160-165.
25. Nematova, Z. (2022). ADVANTAGES OF USING VIDEOS IN ENGLISH LESSONS. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 2(9), 8-12.
26. Mukhabbat, K. Nematova Zebo Lexical innovations of the early English language period (XVI century). *International Engineering for Research and Development.-2020.-№, 5(9)*.
27. Хакимова, М., & Нематова, З. (2021). Лексические инновации периода ранненовоанглийского языка (XVI век). *Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science*, 2(5), 202-207.
28. Tursunbaevna, N. Z. (2022). Types of Interactive Methods of Teaching Foreign Languages in Higher Education Institutions. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 3(10), 151-155.
29. Fayzulloyevna, N. M. (2023). PRAGMATIC VALUES IN PRONUNCIATION OF PHONETICALLY CHANGED WORDS. *International Journal Of Literature And Languages*, 3(02), 63-67.

30. Fayzulloyevna, N. M. (2023). LINGUISTIC STATUS OF PROFESSIONAL JARGONISMS. *International Journal Of Literature And Languages*, 3(03), 17-23.
31. Fayzulloyevna, N. M. (2023). ARCHAISMS IN ENGLISH PROVERBS. *International Journal Of Literature And Languages*, 3(05), 58-64.
32. Fayzulloyevna, N. M., & Rustamovna, B. N. (2023). EXPRESSIVE FUNCTION OF ENGLISH ARGOT IN A LITERARY TEXT. *International Journal Of Literature And Languages*, 3(05), 96-102.
33. Нематова, З. Т., & Хакимова, М. А. (2021). Идеи об идеальном человеке, языке, процветании в эволюции общественно-политических взглядов узбекских джадидов начала XX века. *Central Asian journal of theoretical & applied sciences*, 2(5), 219-224.
34. Нематова, З. Т., & Хакимова, М. А. (2020). Songs in teaching English to young second language learners. *Молодой ученый*, (50), 497-499.
35. Aziza Mirzaeva Shavkatovna. (2022). THE INTERTEXTUAL AND INTERCULTURAL REFERENCES IN LODGE’S CAMPUS NOVELS. *American Journal Of Philological Sciences*, 2(11), 29–35. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajps/Volume02Issue11-05>
36. 10. Aziza, M. (2022). THE THEORY OF INTERTEXTUALITY AS A PARADIGM AND THE IMPACT OF THIS THEORY ON TRANSLATION.
37. Anvarovna, Z. D. Different meaning of the speech verbs say, tell, speak, talk. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(1), 95-97.
38. Samadov, B. S., Jalilova, F. S., Ziyaeva, D. A., Sharipova, D. S., Ozodova, N. X., Norova, H. U., ... & Kudina, O. V. (2020). Pharmacological properties and chemical composition “*Momordica charantia* l”.
39. Samadov, B. S., Jalilova, F. S., Ziyaeva, D. A., Sharipova, D. S., Ozodova, N. X., Norova, H. U., ... & Kudina, O. V. (2020). Pharmacological properties and chemical composition “*Momordica charantia* l”.
40. Rakhmatova M.M., Ziyodullayeva M.E. THE WAYS OF TEACHING HOW TO SPEAK AND THE ROLE OF TEACHER IN THAT PROCESS // *World science*. 2015. №4 (4). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/the-ways-of-teaching-how-to-speak-and-the-role-of-teacher-in-that-process> (дата обращения: 19.09.2023).